

Supplementary Materials: Behavioral strategies of prehistoric and historic children from dental microwear texture analysis

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Statistical analyses

Table S5a: Pairwise comparisons of the groups for anisotropy (*epLsar*).

PH = Point Hope Inuit; NEAN = Neandertals (includes Mousterian –UP but most of the group is composed by Neandertal specimens); EMH = Early modern humans; Amarna = Amarna Egyptians. A = Significance values have been adjusted by the Bonferroni correction for multiple tests. Statistically significant values are marked in bold.

GROUPS	TEST STATISTIC	STD. ERROR	STD. TEST STATISTIC	ADJ. SIG.^A
PH - NEAN	3.688	7.706	.479	1.000
PH - EMH	12.464	6.962	1.790	.440
PH - AMARNA	19.452	6.605	2.945	.019
NEAN - EMH	-8.777	6.324	-1.388	.991
NEAN - AMARNA	-1.765	5.928	-2.659	.047
EMH - AMARNA	-6.988	4.923	-1.420	.935

Table S5b: Pairwise comparisons of the groups for complexity (*Asfc*).

GROUPS	TEST STATISTIC	STD. ERROR	STD. TEST STATISTIC	ADJ. SIG.^A
PH - NEAN	3.750	7.704	0.487	1.000
PH - EMH	12.429	6.961	1.785	0.445
PH - AMARNA	19.452	6.604	2.946	0.019
NEAN - EMH	-8.679	6.323	-1.373	1.000
NEAN - AMARNA	-15.702	5.927	-2.649	0.048

EMH - AMARNA	-7.024	4.922	-1.427	0.922
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Table S5c: Pairwise comparisons of the groups for Scale of maximum complexity (*Smc*).

GROUPS	TEST STATISTIC	STD. ERROR	STD. TEST STATISTIC	ADJ. SIG. ^A
PH - NEAN	3.500	7.699	.455	1.000
PH - EMH	12.071	6.956	1.735	.496
PH - AMARNA	19.202	6.599	2.910	.022
NEAN - EMH	-8.571	6.318	-1.357	1.000
NEAN - AMARNA	-15.702	5.923	-2.651	.048
EMH - AMARNA	-7.131	4.919	-1.450	.883

Table S5d: Pairwise comparisons of the groups for Heterogeneity 3x3 (*HAsfc9*).

GROUPS	TEST STATISTIC	STD. ERROR	STD. TEST STATISTIC	ADJ. SIG. ^A
PH - NEAN	3.750	7.700	.487	1.000
PH - EMH	12.429	6.957	1.787	.444
PH - AMARNA	19.452	6.600	2.947	.019
NEAN - EMH	-8.679	6.319	-1.373	1.000
NEAN - AMARNA	-15.702	5.923	-2.651	.048
EMH - AMARNA	-7.024	4.919	-1.428	.920

Table S5e: Pairwise comparisons of the groups for Heterogeneity 9x9 (*HAsfc81*).

GROUPS	TEST STATISTIC	STD. ERROR	STD. TEST STATISTIC	ADJ. SIG.^A
PH - NEAN	3.750	7.702	.487	1.000
PH - EMH	12.429	6.959	1.786	.445
PH - AMARNA	19.452	6.602	2.946	.019
NEAN - EMH	-8.679	6.321	-1.373	1.000
NEAN - AMARNA	-15.702	5.925	-2.650	.048
EMH - AMARNA	-7.024	4.921	-1.427	.921